

4.5	Summary of quantitative assessment of mass transfer limitation. External (Damköhler number, Da_{ext}) and internal (Weisz–Prater modulus, Φ) mass transfer criteria are calculated for the initial OPC rates obtained at 27 K.	149
4.6	Experimentally derived parameters and goodness-of-fit statistics for five kinetic models regressed against the differential OPC data. Values for the fitted parameters (e.g., k , K , n), their standard errors, and statistical metrics (R^2 , $RMSE$, RSS) are reported for each model at 27 K and 77 K.	154
4.7	Experimentally derived parameters and goodness-of-fit statistics for five kinetic models regressed against the integral OPC data. Values for the fitted parameters (e.g., k , K , n), their standard errors, and statistical metrics (R^2 , $RMSE$, RSS) are reported for each model at 77 K.	158
5.1	Emission factors used in the life cycle assessment.	182
5.2	Summary of the calculated fuel burn, normalised first per passenger and then by distance travelled.	185
A.1	Curve fit parameters for thermal conductivity of brass (W/m·K) from NIST [162]. The fit is valid for temperatures between 5–116 K with an equation range of 5–110 K. The curve fit error is 1.5% relative to the data.	227
A.2	Interpolated thermal conductivity of structural SiC at selected cryogenic temperatures based on digitised data from [163]. Values are given with an uncertainty range corresponding to ± 2 K.	228
A.3	Estimated constant-volume heat capacity C_v of bulk 3C-SiC at cryogenic temperatures, extracted from digitization of Figure 5(a) in [253]. The original data represents specific heat per Si–C pair, which is equivalent to per mole of SiC. This is appropriate for modelling solid-state heat transfer in the packed bed OPC-reactor, as the SiC particles used are dense (30–50 mesh) and not porous, making bulk lattice heat capacity the dominant contribution.	229
A.4	Estimated constant-pressure heat capacity C_p of IONEX [®] at cryogenic temperatures, approximated using experimental data for maghemite ($\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) from digitisation of the heat capacity curve reported in Figure 1 of the study [236]. IONEX [®] is assumed to be a dense, magnetically susceptible iron oxide, and maghemite is selected as a proxy due to its similar physical and magnetic properties. The extracted values are appropriate for packed-bed thermal modelling under the assumption of bulk solid behaviour.	230

A.5	Estimated constant-pressure heat capacity C_p of 70/30 brass at cryogenic temperatures, extracted from [231]. Values were digitized from a graphical source and converted from cal/g·K to J/kg·K. A ± 1 K uncertainty band is included based on curve slope. The conversion used is 1 cal/g·K = 4,184 J/kg·K.	231
B.1	Optional MSC-1 power requirement, in MJ/h, to compress the H₂ feed from 1 to 20 bar and percentage increase of the SEC according to final LH₂ product quality.	233
B.2	Summary of turbo-expander discharge stream specifications for production of LnH₂ (no OPC).	234
B.3	Summary of turbo-expander discharge stream specifications for production of all OPC.	234
B.4	Stream summary for production of LnH₂ (no OPC).	236
B.5	Stream summary for production of 50% LpH₂ (OPC with perfect catalyst).	237
B.6	Stream summary for production of 50% LpH₂ (OPC with imperfect catalyst).	238
B.7	Stream summary for production of 50% LpH₂ (OPC post-liquefaction).	239
B.8	Stream summary for production of 69% LpH₂ (OPC with perfect catalyst).	240
B.9	Stream summary for production of 69% LpH₂ (OPC with imperfect catalyst).	241
B.10	Stream summary for production of 69% LpH₂ (OPC post-liquefaction).	242
B.11	Stream summary for production of 83% LpH₂ (OPC with perfect catalyst).	243
B.12	Stream summary for production of 83% LpH₂ (OPC with imperfect catalyst).	244
B.13	Stream summary for production of 83% LpH₂ (OPC post-liquefaction).	245
B.14	Table S26. Stream summary for production of 95% LpH ₂ (OPC with perfect catalyst).	246
B.15	Table S27. Stream summary for production of 95% LpH ₂ (OPC with imperfect catalyst).	247
B.16	Table S28. Stream summary for production of 95% LpH ₂ (OPC post-liquefaction).	248
B.17	Stream summary for production of 99.6% LpH₂ (OPC with perfect catalyst).	249
B.18	Stream summary for production of 99.6% LpH₂ (OPC with imperfect catalyst).	250

B.19 Table S31. Stream summary for production of 99.6% LpH ₂ (OPC post-liquefaction).	251
B.20 Stream summary of LN₂ production process for the case of LnH₂ production (no OPC).	252
C.1 Experimental results of the OPC at 77 K and 2.3 bar using 0.052 g of catalyst, with varying inlet H ₂ VOL.% in He at ~250 mL min ⁻¹ . The GC-measured o/p ratio is converted to para-H ₂ (%) and corrected using the average room-temperature normal-hydrogen reference. For each concentration, individual runs and the mean ± SD of the corrected para-H ₂ % are reported.	254
C.2 Experimental results of the OPC at 77 K and 2.3 bar using 0.052 g of catalyst, with varying inlet H ₂ VOL.% in He at ~550 mL min ⁻¹ . The GC-measured o/p ratio is converted to para-H ₂ (%) and corrected using the average room-temperature normal-hydrogen reference. For each concentration, individual runs and the mean ± SD of the corrected para-H ₂ % are reported.	255
C.3 Experimental OPC results for the Arrhenius at 100 mL/min. All experiments were performed at a 2.3 bar with a catalyst mass of 0.15 g and at a set-point flow rate of approximately 100 mL/min. Para-H ₂ % were recorded after the outlet concentration had reached steady state.	256
C.4 Experimental OPC results for the Arrhenius at 100 mL/min. All experiments were performed at a 2.3 bar with a catalyst mass of 0.15 g and at a set-point flow rate of approximately 150 mL/min. Para-H ₂ % were recorded after the outlet concentration had reached steady state.	257
C.5 Experimental OPC results for the Arrhenius at 100 mL/min. All experiments were performed at a 2.3 bar with a catalyst mass of 0.15 g and at a set-point flow rate of approximately 200 mL/min. The experimental para-H ₂ % was recorded after the outlet concentration had reached steady state.	258
C.6 Experimental OPC results for the Arrhenius at 100 mL/min. All experiments were performed at a 2.3 bar with a catalyst mass of 0.15 g and at a set-point flow rate of approximately 550 mL/min. The experimental para-H ₂ % was recorded after the outlet concentration had reached steady state.	259
C.7 Temperature dependence of the rate constant at 100 mL/min. Values used to construct the Arrhenius plot (i.e., ln <i>k</i> vs 1/ <i>T</i>) for the OPC between 27 and 77 K at a set-point flow rate of 100 ml/min. For each set-point temperature, the initial rate analysis ($r = kC_{H_2}$ yields a rate constant, <i>k</i>	260

C.8	Temperature dependence of the rate constant at 150 mL/min. Values used to construct the Arrhenius plot (i.e., $\ln k$ vs $1/T$) for the OPC between 27 and 77 K at a set-point flow rate of 150 ml/min. For each set-point temperature, the initial rate analysis ($r = kC_{H_2}$ yields a rate constant, k	260
C.9	Temperature dependence of the rate constant at 200 mL/min. Values used to construct the Arrhenius plot (i.e., $\ln k$ vs $1/T$) for the OPC between 27 and 77 K at a set-point flow rate of 200 ml/min. For each set-point temperature, the initial rate analysis ($r = kC_{H_2}$ yields a rate constant, k	260
C.10	Temperature dependence of the rate constant at 550 mL/min. Values used to construct the Arrhenius plot (i.e., $\ln k$ vs $1/T$) for the OPC between 27 and 77 K at a set-point flow rate of 550 ml/min. For each set-point temperature, the initial rate analysis ($r = kC_{H_2}$ yields a rate constant, k	260
C.11	Summary of quantitative assessment of mass transfer limitation. External (Damköhler number, Da_{ext}) and internal (Weisz–Prater modulus, Φ) mass transfer criteria are calculated for the initial OPC rates obtained between 27 K and 77 K at 100 ml/min.	261
C.12	Summary of quantitative assessment of mass transfer limitation. External (Damköhler number, Da_{ext}) and internal (Weisz–Prater modulus, Φ) mass transfer criteria are calculated for the initial OPC rates obtained between 27 K and 77 K at 150 ml/min.	261
C.13	Summary of quantitative assessment of mass transfer limitation. External (Damköhler number, Da_{ext}) and internal (Weisz–Prater modulus, Φ) mass transfer criteria are calculated for the initial OPC rates obtained between 27 K and 77 K at 200 ml/min.	261
C.14	Summary of quantitative assessment of mass transfer limitation. External (Damköhler number, Da_{ext}) and internal (Weisz–Prater modulus, Φ) mass transfer criteria are calculated for the initial OPC rates obtained between 27 K and 77 K at 550 ml/min.	262
D.1	Summary of the key values used in estimating the fuel burn for kerosene and liquid hydrogen in a Boeing 787-9 aircraft.	266
D.2	Summary of the calculated fuel burn, normalised first per passenger and then by distance travelled.	266
D.3	GWP results for 25-99.6% LpH₂ production (gCO_{2,eq}/MJ_{LH₂}) accounting for hydrogen production <i>via</i> water electrolysis, liquefaction, transportation, boil-off leakage (up to 15%), replenishment of the boil-off with LH ₂ of the same p-H ₂ % for both the grid-based and wind-based processes.	268